

PART A: CURRENT PAYMENT CONFIRMATION INTERFACES IN ENGLISH

Screens 1, 2

PART B: CURRENT PAYMENT CONFIRMATION INTERFACES IN KINYARWANDA

Screens 1, 2

Description (PART A & B)

- 1 - Confirmation after sending money to an individual (07xxxxxxx)
- 2 - Confirmation after sending money to a business (MoMo code)

PART C: PROPOSED PAYMENT CONFIRMATION INTERFACES IN ENGLISH

Screens 4a, 4b, 5a, 5b, 6, 7

PART D: PROPOSED PAYMENT CONFIRMATION INTERFACES IN KINYARWANDA

Screens 4a, 4b, 5a, 5b, 6, 7

Description (PART C & D)

4a - A private screen for merchants (A Well formatted response with the date and other essential information for the merchant to look at)

4b - A private screen for customers after 4a is confirmed (Contains the new balance and the fee)

5a - Similar to 4a but for regular users (07xxxx)

5b - Similar to 5a but for momo business codes

6 - MoMo USSD prompt supplies a secret set by the merchant to the customer. So the customer has to supply the correct secret to convince the merchant the payment went through.

7 - The merchant has a challenge to complete on the customer's device ussd prompt, so the customer hands the device to the merchant to input their code as a final step instead.

Note: Although we were not able to depict it on a screen, we explored the concept of allowing merchants to add multiple recipients for SMS payment confirmations. This feature would enable a merchant to subscribe employees to receive these notifications and easily unsubscribe them when their contracts are terminated. This functionality addresses the challenge of needing to leave a dedicated device at the point of sale. A question was dedicated to this in the interview guide.

9:30

1

You have sent 1,200 RWF to 250795841311. Your balance is 64,014 RWF. Thank you for using MTN Mobile Money.

Cancel

Send

*

0

#

+

Recents

Contacts

SIMBoard

9:30

2

Y'ello. You have paid 1,200 RWF to OKEY MARKET LTD., 123897. Fee 0 RWF. Transaction ID 32055055507. Your Mobile Money account balance is 65,234 RWF.

Cancel

Send

*

0

#

+

Recents

Contacts

SIMBoard

9:30

1

Wohereje 1,200 RWF kuri
250795841311. Usigaranye 65,234
RWF. Murakoze gukoresha MTN
Mobile Money.

Cancel

Send

*

0

#

+

Recents

Contacts

SIMBoard

9:30

2

Y'ello. wishyuye 1,200 RWF kuri
OKEY MARKET LTD, 123897. Ikiguzi
0 RWF. Transaction ID
32055055507. Usigaranye 14,041
RWF kuri konti yawe ya mobile
money.

Cancel

Send

*

0

#

+

Recents

Contacts

SIMBoard

9:30

4a

You have sent 1,200 RWF to:
Ishami Muganirisa Teganzo
(250795841311)
at 2025-09-13 18:52

TxID 21003022
n Next

Cancel

Send

*

0

#

+

Recents

Contacts

SIMBoard

9:30

4b

Fee 20 RWF.

Your Mobile Money account balance
is now 64,014 RWF.

Cancel

Send

*

0

#

+

Recents

Contacts

SIMBoard

9:30

5a

You have paid 1,200 RWF to:
OKEY MARKET LTD.
(123897)
at 2025-09-13 18:51

TxID 32055055507
n Next

Cancel

Send

*

0

#

+

Recents

Contacts

SIMBoard

9:30

5b

Fee 0 RWF.

Your Mobile Money account balance
is now 65,234 RWF.

Cancel

Send

*

0

#

+

Recents

Contacts

SIMBoard

9:30

6

You have paid 1,200 RWF to:
OKEY MARKET LTD.
(123897)
at 2025-09-13 18:51
TxID 32055055507

Verification code: 125730

Cancel

Send

*

0

#

+

Recents

Contacts

SIMBoard

9:30

7

You have paid 1,200 RWF to:
OKEY MARKET LTD.
(123897)
at 2025-09-13 18:51
TxID 32055055507

Enter verification code:

Cancel

Send

*

0

#

+

Recents

Contacts

SIMBoard

9:30

4a

Wohereje 1,200 RWF kuri:
Ishami Muganirisa Teganzo
(250795841311)
kuwa 2025-09-13 18:52

TxID 21003022.
n Komeza

Cancel

Send

*

0

#

+

Recents

Contacts

SIMBoard

9:30

4b

Ikiguzi 20 RWF.

Usigaranye 65,234 RWF kuri konti yawe ya mobile money.

Cancel

Send

*

0

#

+

Recents

Contacts

SIMBoard

9:30

5a

Wishyuye 1,200 RWF kuri:
OKEY MARKET LTD.
(123897)
kuwa 2025-09-13 18:52

TxID 32055055507.
n Komeza

Cancel

Send

*

0

#

+

Recents

Contacts

SIMBoard

9:30

5b

Ikiguzi 0 RWF.

Usigaranye 65,234 RWF kuri konti yawe ya mobile money.

Cancel

Send

*

0

#

+

Recents

Contacts

SIMBoard

9:30

6

Wishyuye 1,200 RWF kuri:
OKEY MARKET LTD.
(123897)
kuwa 2025-09-13 18:52
TxID 32055055507.

Kode y'iyemezabumenyi: 125730

Cancel

Send

*

0

#

+

Recents

Contacts

SIMBoard

9:30

7

Wishyuye 1,200 RWF kuri:
OKEY MARKET LTD.
(123897)
kuwa 2025-09-13 18:52
TxID 32055055507.

Injiza kode y'iyemezabumenyi:

Cancel

Send

*

0

#

+

Recents

Contacts

SIMBoard